

CHARACTERIZATION TRAITS IN AHMAD MAHMOOD AND AHLEM MOSTEGHANEM NOVELS

RASGOS DE CARACTERIZACIÓN EN LAS NOVELAS AHMAD MAHMOOD Y AHLEM MOSTEGHANEM

RESUMEN

El objetivo de este artículo fue evaluar el elemento de carácter y caracterización en dos historias: "Vecinos" del autor iraní Ahmad Mahmoud y "Memorias del cuerpo" del escritor argelino Ahlem Mosteghanemi. La metodología de investigación fue el análisis histórico y de contenido. Los resultados mostraron que la diferencia más importante entre las dos novelas es la forma ficticia y el lenguaje de los personajes.

Palabras clave: Caracterización, Vecinos, Memorias del Cuerpo, Ahmad Mahmoud, Ahlem Mosteghanemi

ABSTRACT

The aim of this article was to evaluate to element of character and characterization in two stories: "Neighbors" by Iranian author Ahmad Mahmoud and "Memories of Body" by Algerian writer Ahlem Mosteghanemi. Research methodology was historical and content analysis. Results showed that the most important difference between the two novels is the fictional form and the language of characters.

Keywords: Characterization, Neighbors, Memories of Body, Ahmad Mahmoud, Ahlem Mosteghanemi

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INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this article is to evaluate the element of character and characterization techniques in two fictions Ahmed Mahmoud's "Neighbors" and Ahlem Mosteghanemi's "Memories of Body" in the form of American-style comparative literature, because the American school does not know the condition, the effect and influence between the two works, while the French school believes that we can adapt two works that affect one another (Taghavi, 2017). Comparative literature provides a space for the reader to become familiar with the culture of the countries where two writers grew up and write their own story and compare these cultures. Iran and Algeria are two Muslim countries with many cultural similarities and the background of anti-colonial political struggles in both countries is shared.

Characters are the best forms in which a writer can, on the one hand, make his dreams and aspirations come true, and, on the other hand, his hatreds and regrets and express his thoughts and feelings in their language, because the intermediation of characters, the amount acceptance of the author's thoughts increases and makes them credible. Interestingly, the character, among the elements of the story, takes the most influence from other elements; For example, the place in the personality and the atmosphere of dialogue between the characters is influential.

The prisoner's character is different from being, the character of the resident with the immigrant and the rural personality is different from the city, and this shows the effect of the place on the personality. Characterization is, in fact, believable in the mental and unreal images in the mind of the author, and the writer uses his characterization techniques to show his experience and skill in fiction and the critic can find out how well the author succeeds in his story design by evaluating and analyzing characterization in the story.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Independent research has been conducted in the area of critique and analysis of the novels Neighbors and Memories of Body, but no scholar has ever considered these two novels from any angle. In general, it can be said that the fictional literature of Iran and Algeria has not been seriously criticized, and this article is an attempt in this regard. Among the studies that independently evaluated these two novels, we can mention the following:

1 -Developmental constructive critique of the novel Neighbors. This article focuses on the constructive theory of Goldman, and employs it in this novel, and evaluates the relationship between form and content. In general, the area of sociology of this novel is studied.

2 -Characterization in the novel Neighbors. This article evaluates a variety of characters in the novel and their degree of involvement in the story process.

3 -The study of the story elements in the novel Neighbors by Ahmad Mahmoud (Ebrahim Tabar, Mansourian & Ebrahim Tabar, 2016). This article focuses on the narrative of the story and analyzes the content axes of the novel.

METHODOLOGY

This is a qualitative research conducted by content analysis method and data obtained by deductive analysis method. In the first step, the main themes of the text were identified. Then the items related to each of these themes were categorized, and finally, each item was coded. In the final step, the frequency and frequency of each of these items were evaluated and compared.

RESULTS

AN OVERVIEW OF NEIGHBORS AND MEMORIES OF BODY

"Neighbors" is the narration of the young physical and spiritual maturity called Khalid. His mental maturity is a political struggle with the goal of nationalizing the oil industry in Iran. The author of the Neighborhood novel tries to bring the hero to the story in different positions and to get acquainted with different people to portray the path to his political development and political maturity.

"Memories of Body" is also a personal narrative of a militant called Khalid who, by losing one hand during the revolution in Algeria, chooses painting as a way of expressing confrontation with the new world. The centerpiece of love is another point that puts the two novels together.

"Siyah Cheshm" in Neighbors and "Ahlem" in Memories of Body are the effects of this love, and in a deeper look, they are the symbol of homeland. In the constraints of choosing between love for the homeland and the love of women, Khalid in the novel Neighbors elects his love for the home and goes to political struggles and goes to prison, and Khalid in Memories of Body, who has always had the pain of love and separation in the chest loses his own hands in the war.

The main difference between the Neighbors and the Memories of Body is in the form of the story, because Neighbors is a realist story, and the use of techniques such as "accident tracing at the time of occurrence" and "assembling" and, consequently, "illusion of time" makes it a completely novel realistic with a classic

form. While *Memories of Body*, on the contrary, is a symbolic novel, due to the time spent on it and it is a modern novel, because it begins with sentences that mark the end of an endless love, and from that point on, the circular motion of the book begins at the adventures of the story; in other words, the story ends from the end to the first.

While the *Neighbors* portray the first steps in the maturity in the hero's maturity of the story, and ultimately, his political and social failure means that the time in it is linear, not circular motion. The dispensation time in the *Memories of Body* is that in the first bounty, Khalid talks about a book called "The Forgetting screw" written by his mistress Al Jazeera.

The next chapter describes the Khalid Painting Exhibition in Paris and the first meeting with Ahlem, the daughter of Si Tahir, a major Algerian militant. In the following chapters, we will find out with the fluid flow of mind; line to line from youth and adolescence, and the struggles of Khalid and his friendship with Si Tahir and other revolutionary fighters and his beloved Katherine, and his attitudes at the milestones of his life, such as when he lost his hand, when he acquainted with Khalid and when he fell in love. In the sixth chapter of the book, we read that 'Hassan' Khalid's brother has been killed with a bullet by mistake, and now Khalid has returned to Algeria and his city, Qostantanaya, for the funeral. This chapter is simultaneously the beginning and the continuation of the first chapter, and indeed the reason for Khalid's trip to Algeria. A journey leading to the new book of Ahlam and seeing his interview in the Algerian magazine is a spark to begin writing this novel.

It should be said that the novel *Memories of Body*, in terms of content, is formed on the basis of a pure love, and continues with a drowning in this love; drowning is a pleasing and sometimes melancholy of the pain and suffering that the love of the homeland and the love of a woman, which also somehow translates into earth, mother and homeland, has brought on Khalid's body.

The narrator of the *Memories of Body*, Khalid, narrates the story in the way of the narrator of the first person, the entire knowledgeable one, to the narrator's mind. Khalid is a combatant man who becomes a painter due to the loss of one hand during the struggle of the revolution; but *Neighbors*, like other works of socialist literature, is formed on the basis of a political-social maturity and the birth of a struggle nucleus (Khalid, Pendar, Bidar), in which there are striking streaks of love.

The angle of view in the book *Neighbors* is on the wisdom of the whole, and of course there are several first person narrators; while the *Memories of Body* book is narrated only from the language of Khalid, the first person and hero of the story in which the wisdom of the whole is limited to the mind of the speaker. Both of these

methods have their own particular advantages, for example, the unknowing total presence of a person can help the author to express the purpose of the story, to help the author more open, but also the presence of a narrator, and also the first narrator of the person.

He speaks more of himself and his mental states and inner layers for the audience, and ultimately the audience, faces characters that have more clarity. The streamlining technique of flow of mind is also in two stories. In the Neighbors, this technique is further utilized with the scattered singularities of characters, Khalid, Pendar, and.... In the novel of Memories of Body, we confront with many hymns of main hero Khalid. He is mostly lonely, and this loneliness and his ingenious, sensual and artistic spirit have made these hymns deeper.

SYNOPSIS OF THE MEMORIES OF BODY

During his revolutionary struggles, Khalid is jailed in the age of 16 and is a high school student. In prison, he is with "Si Tahir" great Algerian warrior in one cell. Nine years later, at the age of 25, he joined the Liberation Front and rejoined Si Tahir again. But this time, this struggle will lead to the loss of one hand and the first turning point in his life. Khalid is transferred to Tunisia for hand surgery. Before transferring, Si Tahir wants to take care of his newborn baby.

He tells Khalid to give his daughter a birth certificate and name her "Ahlem". In this struggle, "Si Tahir" is martyred. On the other hand, the Palestinian poetry, "Ziad", is in love with Khalid. Ahlem, who is 25 years old, is in Paris and lives with his uncle's sister, Si Sharif. Si Sharif is a man who has entered politics and, to the point where he has already been able to name himself the brother of his martyr's Si Tahir for his place and wealth and influence. Khalid invites Si Sharif for his exhibition, but he sends his daughter and his brother's daughter to replace him because of his occupation.

A visit that leads to the beginning of a love that is full of prohibitions, negations and sanctities, and ultimately failures in Khalid. Khalid invites Ahlem to see the panels to his home, and in the same invitation he acquaints him with books by friend of poet Ziad warrior. In the late summer days, Ziad and Ahlem meet each other. Until now, the story is just the truth, but from here on, the inclinations and suspicions of Khalid are involved in adventure. Sometime later, it is reported that Ziad has been killed in the war. Khalid now experiences a torture of conscience, and Ahlem is even farther away from him. Until one day, the voice of Si Sharif from the other side of the phone gives Khalid the Ahlem wedding news with a civilian military authority in Algeria and will invite him to attend Ahlem's wedding as spiritual father of Ahlem.

Personality in Novels Neighbor and Memories of Body: Neighbors: Characters of Neighbors novel are simple and hardworking people of society in the years 1950 to 1952, and experience political events of these years. Since Ahmad Mahmoud had been thinking of socialism, (Ebrahim Tabar et al., 2016), his characters are either from the ordinary people of the society or from loyalists to the Communist Party and insurgents Party. In the communist literature, the hero must come from the people and be formed in the face of popular protests and mass struggles, which is the main character of the novel, Khalid. The language of characters in the neighbors is chosen according to their social class, which often comes from the lower classes of society. Ahmad Mahmoud insists on his reader in his Neighbor's novel those who were members of the Communist Party did not have any knowledge of the party and Khalid is also randomly drawn to this party. Perhaps he wanted to say that there was no possibility of knowing the Party in Iran, or that there was nothing to be known for, since it was completely imitation of the Communist Party of Russia.

Memories of Body: The characters of the novel Memories of Body, unlike Neighbors novel, are all selected and among high-profile characters. Khalid, Si Tahir and Si Sharif are among the old fighters who played a major role in the victory of the Algerian Revolution. It is better to say that Memories of Body is the story of the second generation of the revolution. Another feature of this novel is the dynamism of most of its characters, because they are constantly changing; changes in moral and behavioral dimensions that are not predictable. The novel's author, Ahlem Mosteghanemi, does not overlook the slightest changes in the hero of the story, Khalid, and all of his lower dimensions and features of his personality dimensions do not turn away from joys, sorrows, emotions, expectations, failures, jealousy... It describes them well and in detail, and we see his gradual changes throughout the book. Interestingly, despite the fact that Ahlem is considered the main character and has a wonderful effect on Khalid and his life is followed alongside Khalid's character, there is not much detail about him, and Ahlem's character is always dumb. Her personality must be recognized during her speeches and remarks. She is an open minded, conscious, intelligent and beautiful woman while adhering to certain traditions of her country Algeria.

Major and minor characters: The main character of both the novels of the Neighbors and the Memories of Body is Khalid, who is also the narrator of the story in Memories of Body, along with "Ahlem". In the case of sub-characters, the presence of these characters in the story is necessary because it stains the story and adds to the story of the depth and texture and contributes to the function and importance of the main heroes. And it may be said that the advantage of the presence of sub-personalities is to make the story space more realistic and more natural. (Kabayeva, Mussabaev & Madaliev, 2018) The most important sub-characters of the Neighbor's novel are Mother and father of Khalid, Leyla, Ibrahim,

Rahim Kharakchi, Uncle Bandar, Mohammad Mechanic, Sanam and Afagh. In the novel *Memories of Body*: Ziad, Katharine, Si Tahir, Hessian, Si Sharif and Nasser are considered to be minor characters because of the role they play in introducing the main characters of the novel.

DISCUSSION

CHARACTERIZATION TRAITS IN THE NOVEL MEMORIES OF BODY

Characterization in the story is divided into direct and indirect ways:

Direct Characterization: The author defines character in direct characterization style; that is, he explicitly tells us that what features does the character have. He says, for example, that he is indifferent and has nothing to do with anything. Examples of direct characterization in two stories:

In stories where their viewing angles are based on the wisdom of the whole, the writer describes the state of their characters and their appearance. It is worth saying that the angles of view in both novels are the wise of whole; of course, the wise of whole is infinite in the *Neighbors* and in the *Memories of Body*, the wise of whole is limited to the mind of the poet who is the main character of the story. So, in these two novels, we expect more direct evidence of characterization, while it is not the case, and has been used more indirectly.

Indirect Characterization: In the indirect method, the component implies the whole; for example, the drawing of fingers and their so-called "breaking," implies the nervousness of the individual. Behavior, speech, name, environment and apparent personality can be characterization tools. Characterization in the *Neighbor's* novel is more indirect. This style is also used in the *Memories of Body*. In general, it can be said that direct characterization in these two novels does not share much. First of all, this will increase the involvement of the reader, because in the indirect characterization method, this reader judges the characters, and secondly, the sense of suspension in the book becomes greater; that means the reader will continue to follow the story with a keen interest. In this way, the author is able to abandon himself from the characterization by writing a few words and advance the story more quickly. In indirect characterization, the author gives the reader information indirectly through behavior, thoughts, speech, and even personality name.

1. Description: In describing the description they say: "A stream that we are familiar with the reader with the characters of the story". The description of

appearance, face, body, and even personality dress can be from characterization traits that, through permissiveness and subtlety, and metaphor, characterize personality in a succinct way, and delineates straightforwardness and direct expression. For example, in the Neighbor's novel, instead of saying that Mohammed Mechanic is a hard-working, nationalist, and revolutionary person, this is the description about him:

"It's late at night for some days when it's time to work. In front of it, I see a white bar on his chest. The white bar was a fabric that the oil workers and political fighters attached to their chests during the nationalization of the oil industry and it was written on it: Oil industry should be nationalized.

Ahlem Mosteghanemi, who narrates the story in the language of a painter, with the obsession of a painter in the choice of theme and the scene and brush and the dimensions of work, and finally the choice of quality and condition of colors, to describe the characters of the story. The use of a kind of calm and emotional prose full of exquisite metaphors and strong sympathies combined with a spectacularly remarkable contributing to characterization has given a new dimension. The plurality of literary arrays in the Memories of Body is so much that in most cases, the poetic aspects of this work overcome its fictional aspect and brought the language of the novel closer to poetry.

2. Name: Another way of indirect characterization is to use the name. The writer can easily define the general lines of the personality by choosing a name, and "by creating a semantic and intuitive relationship between the character structure and his name, they will show some internal and external features of characters" (Okhovat, 2018, p: 166) Character naming cannot be random but in line with the purpose and the general context of the story, and if we look at the names of the characters in these two novels, we can guess their moral and behavioral features. For example, in the novels Neighbors, "Osta Hadad" is a fanatic who is strong in his superstitious beliefs like iron, and nothing can disturb his thoughts. The names of Ali Sheytan and Siyah Cheshm also indicate the inner and outer characteristics of the personality. In "Memories of Body", Si Tahir (Si, stands for Seyyed, meaning "Master and Supreme"), is the leader of the warrior who is martyred. His life and death are like his name. Si Sharif is the brother of Si Tahir who is abusing his position as a martyr's brother. In fact, Si Sharif does not remain Noble and his name becomes a corollary of his personality! Ahlem means dreams, patient and dignified. Hassan means handsome and includes a large section of the population of Algeria.

3. Behavior: Action or behavior is another trait used by the author for Characterization. For example, in the introduction of the main character of the story, Khalid, Mosteghanemi could write very explicitly and directly from the first

person's promise that I love my homeland and love the struggle for the homeland... but he chooses another way.

4. Conversation: Dialogue is used as an important and delicate tool in Characterization. Character in the story has no meaning without conversation; unless it is completely alone, although in that case it also requires internal dialogue or recall of conversations in the mind of the character.

5. Symbolization: Another trait of characterization can be the symbolization of choosing a name. In this characterization trait, "the author deals with symbolic descriptions of acts and objects". The author is able to abstract the space of the story by symbolizing names and give it a large and wide volume. The Neighbors novel is considered a realistic symbolic novel. The technique used by Ahmed Mahmoud in this novel is 'create space', 'emphasis', and 'repetition'.

In the same way, he gives readers clues and introduces him to symbolic scenes. In this regard, he uses the elements and scene objects in symbolic character processing (Atash Soda & Hariri Jahromi, 2017).

In the story of "Memories of Body," Khalid can be the symbol of the fighters and warriors of the path to freedom and pride of the homeland, which are always endless and eternal (Atash Soda & Hariri Jahromi, 2017). Ahlem is the symbol of the homeland and motherland, which Khalid loves as a warrior of the country, and in the length of the story, this love never, fades away. Khalid's emphasis on painting the "bridges of the homeland" can refer to the concept of communication that lies at the core of the bridge, the relationship between man and homeland or the connection between Algeria and Europe.

CONCLUSION

The way of characterization in the two novels is more indirect, which is the same as the virtual implications and the implication of the component as a whole. In other words, there is not much information about the appearance of characters. Despite the fact that in many memoirs and biographies of the characters, the author could easily, by expressing an "adjective" of the promise of the narrator, advance the story faster, but he did not do this. The indirect characterization form involved the reader's involvement in advancing the novel increases, because it is the reader who judges the characters. On the other hand, it gives the sense of suspension in the story. Description, name picking, behavior, dialogue, symbolization are traits of indirect characterization, which are used in both novels.

Both Ahmad Mahmoud and Mostaghanemi have used their own techniques to present the story to the reader. In *Neighbors*, techniques such as "explain incident at the time of occurrence" and "assembling" and, consequently, "time illusion" have been used. While in *Memories of Body*, the timing technique is used, because it begins with sentences that indicate the story of endless love, and from this point, the circular motion of the book begins, move to the storytelling stories. In other words, the story comes from the end to the beginning, but in *Neighbors*, the course of time is linear, not circular motion.

Khalid's characters are similar in two stories. Both of them are fighting and have an introvert character. Meanwhile, both are lovers.

Women's violence and the lack of involvement in determining their own destinies and getting entangled in a male-dominated society are in both novels. "Ahlem", although she is an intellectual girl and she studies in Paris and has many conscripts; but eventually she married on expediency to escape from the past. Apparently, this is a story shared by many girls from the eastern lands, whether Iran or Algeria.

The *Neighborhood* (or *Neighbors*) novel, due to the names of characters, places, and other cultural elements, has a completely southern color and smell, and in a completely realistic manner in Iran after the coup of August 28, 1953, and for this reason, it is a historical and political novel. The *Memories of Body* also revolves around the struggle and fighters of the revolution in Algeria (1954-1962), a revolution that leads to the independence of Algeria from France. The story is narrated 25 years after the days of the war, but it always returns to the days of war and the ideals of war. The main character of the story is in doubt in the internal struggle between choosing Ahlem as a mistress or a relationship with him as the survival of his dear commanding team, Si Tahir. There is the same doubt in the mind of Khalid, the hero of *Neighbors*, when he wants to choose among the national duty, political struggle and material love, one who will ultimately choose one which ultimately overcomes national sentiment on personal inclinations and he pursues political activities and eventually falls into jail.

The *Neighbors'* book has several first-person narrators apart from the wise of the whole, while the book of *Memories of Body* reads only Khalid's first person and hero of the story. Both of these have their own specific difficulties. For example, the wise presence of the whole can help the writer to express the purpose and story of the story and help make the author more open. But, on the other hand, the presence of a narrator, and the first person's narrator, makes him speak more of himself and his mental states and inner layers for the audience, and ultimately, the audience faces more clearly distinguished characters.

The story of both books goes through the fluid flow of mind narrative technique. In the *Neighbors*, this technique is used more often with the scattered parodies of characters, Khalid, Pandar, and so on. In the *Memories of Body*, we are haunted with many anecdotes by Khalid. He is mostly lonely and this alone with his introverted spirit and, on the other hand, his artistry, and his sensitivity has been led to the deepening of this anecdotes.

In two novels, the political and social conditions are dealt with in two completely different ways. *Neighbors*, like most of the poems and stories that have been written in the years 1951 to 1953, the peak of the struggle for the nationalization of the oil industry until the August 28 coup, spark protest and defeat, and more are narrators of party-political struggles, and how a popular hero with doctrines Party formed. This hero is the same Khalid who became a pragmatic human being after becoming acquainted with the Pendar and Bidar that is a member of the Communist Party, and his life is targeted. *Memories of Body* is also a celebration of the political struggle against the French invaders, 25 years after the days of the war, but it always returns to the days of war and its aspirations, and in general it is the narrator of the struggle; of course, Khalid, who is the symbol of Algeria, never reaches Ahlem (the dream of democracy and freedom) that he dreams of reaching, and thus this novel also narrates defeats.

In the context of the tune of narrators and multi-sounding novels, it seems that Ms. Mostaghanemi has been more successful. Although all the characters were educated and this could have been very similar, but through the words he has chosen for each character, we find a way to know the class and level of understanding, and ultimately within the characters. But in Ahmad Mahmoud's novel, they all talk like each other, and not only the difference in the amount of information and education among the characters is not seen, but there is no difference between male and female narratives as well, while female narratives are full of details, full of emotions that we see in the Ahlem dialogues.

The main narrator of the *Memories of Body* is a man, and he has put himself all the time in his place instead of this man's narrator. Though we can see streaks of feminine writing in the *Memories of Body* novel but Miss Mostaghanemi, using the strong anecdotes has gained a large amount of information in the field of struggle and painting, and many of the inner emotions of men, and, in fact, he has come up with a male narrative.

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